

Equilibrium sampling of suspended particulate matter as a universal proxy for fish and mussel monitoring

Theo Wernicke^{a,b,*}, Sebastian Abel^{a,1}, Beate I. Escher^{c,d}, Jan Koschorreck^e, Heinz Rüdell^f, Annika Jahnke^{a,b}

^a UFZ Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, Department of Ecological Chemistry, Permoserstr. 15, 04318 Leipzig, Germany

^b Institute for Environmental Research, RWTH Aachen University, 52074 Aachen, Germany

^c UFZ Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, Department of Cell Toxicology, Permoserstr. 15, 04318 Leipzig, Germany

^d Environmental Toxicology, Center for Applied Geoscience, Eberhard Karls University Tübingen, Schnarrenbergstr. 94-96, 72076 Tübingen, Germany

^e Federal Environment Agency (Umweltbundesamt), Corrensplatz 1, 14195 Berlin, Germany

^f Fraunhofer Institute for Molecular Biology and Applied Ecology (IME), 57392 Schmallenberg, Germany

ARTICLE INFO

Edited by: Professor Bing Yan

Keywords:

Suspended particulate matter (SPM)

Passive equilibrium sampling

Bioaccumulation

Fish

Mussels

Proxy

ABSTRACT

Bioaccumulation of persistent and hydrophobic organic compounds in the aquatic environment puts secondary consumers, such as fish, at risk. To assess their exposure, monitoring programs with high numbers of individuals have been conducted worldwide over decades that require major efforts and raise ethical issues. This study aimed at testing suspended particulate matter (SPM) as an alternative and accessible abiotic matrix to estimate the internal exposure concentrations of such chemicals in fish and mussels. Muscle tissues of bream (*Abramis brama*), tissues of zebra mussels (*Dreissena polymorpha*) and SPM were collected from four major German rivers, Elbe, Danube, Saar and Saale, in 2018 within the national monitoring program of the German Environmental Specimen Bank. We used (i) total solvent extraction for biota samples to quantify the lipid-normalized concentrations of polychlorinated biphenyls, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and hexachlorobenzene and (ii) passive equilibrium sampling of SPM to derive equilibrium partitioning concentrations in lipids and (iii) set these independent data sets into context. Since the ratio of lipid-normalized concentration / equilibrium partitioning concentration in lipids was in most cases < 1.0, SPM may serve as a conservative proxy for the internal concentration of bream and mussels, although bream of high age (i.e., older than 10 years) showed a tendency for this ratio to exceed 1.0. This observation indicates that age-dependent biomagnification can exceed the predictions based on thermodynamic equilibrium relative to SPM.

1. Introduction

Aquatic organisms are exposed to persistent and bioaccumulative hydrophobic organic compounds (HOCs) from their surrounding environment and food sources. Depending on the role of an organism in the ecosystem and the physico-chemical properties of the HOCs, the organism can bioaccumulate such hazardous substances by bioconcentration, i.e., direct uptake from the abiotic environment, and biomagnification, i.e., uptake from food. Macdonald et al. (2002) described bioconcentration as a partitioning process via the gills without an increase in fugacity and biomagnification via the gastrointestinal tract as non-equilibrium process, where the substance concentration and

fugacity in lipids of an organism are increased. This increase is due to the digestion of lipids that results in a decreased fugacity capacity of the lipids and hence an increase in fugacity of the digested food, thus causing an increased fugacity in the consumer. Qiao et al. (2000) found that the gill uptake dominated for substances with a $\log K_{OW} < 5$ in rainbow trout, whereas the uptake via the gastrointestinal tract was the most relevant uptake route for more hydrophobic substances. Compounds with a $\log K_{OW} < 5$ typically do not biomagnify in aquatic food webs, whereas compounds with higher $\log K_{OW}$ have decreasing elimination rates via respiratory surfaces and, unless they are subject to significant biotransformation, accumulate in aquatic organisms and may biomagnify along the food chain (Gobas et al., 1999). Furthermore, the

* Corresponding author at: UFZ Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, Department of Ecological Chemistry, Permoserstr. 15, 04318 Leipzig, Germany. E-mail addresses: theo.wernicke@ufz.de (T. Wernicke), annika.jahnke@ufz.de (A. Jahnke).

¹ Present address: Stockholm University, Department of Environmental Science, Svante Arrhenius väg 8, SE-114 18 Stockholm, Sweden.

trophic position of a species in the food web is known to have a significant influence on the extent of biomagnification (Kidd et al., 1998).

HOCS show biomagnification at elevated trophic levels. In the aquatic environment, those high trophic level organisms usually are top predators and piscivorous fish that occupy key positions in the ecosystem. Furthermore, such fish are part of the human diet and hence relevant for human exposure. To protect top predators and human health, fish are subject to monitoring programs, where individual fish of certain indicator species are sacrificed on a regular basis for target analysis of regulated contaminants, e.g., the priority substances in biota defined by the European Water Framework Directive (Fliedner et al., 2016). However, this effort is labor-intensive and the obtained monitoring data can be challenged by the loss of less persistent analytes during the complex extraction and clean-up procedures and by high variability between data from the sampled individuals. Depending on their age, trophic position, nutrition and health status, individuals of the same species and at the same site can vary strongly in their lipid-based concentrations (McIntyre and Beauchamp, 2007; McLeod et al., 2014), therefore large sample sizes are required. This variability makes it challenging to compare the contamination levels over time or between different water bodies. Furthermore, monitoring programs raise ethical concerns because common procedures imply regular sacrificing of a substantial number of vertebrates.

In the pursuit of standardized and animal-free alternative monitoring concepts, fugacity-based approaches promise realistic and comparable exposure estimates provided the system under consideration is in equilibrium (Gobas et al., 2018). Equilibrium partitioning concentrations in a polymeric reference phase, e.g. thin silicone films at equilibrium with sediment ($C_{\text{Sil}=\text{Sed}}$) (Jahnke et al., 2012, including conceptual figure; Jahnke et al., 2014; Schäfer et al., 2015) can be translated into concentrations in model lipids at thermodynamic equilibrium with the sediment ($C_{\text{Lip}=\text{Sed}}$) with the help of independently determined lipid/silicone partition coefficients ($K_{\text{Lip}=\text{Sil}}$): $C_{\text{Lip}=\text{Sed}} = C_{\text{Sil}=\text{Sed}} \times K_{\text{Lip}=\text{Sil}}$ (Jahnke et al., 2008; Gilbert et al., 2016; Smedes et al., 2017). Polymer-based passive sampling has also been applied in water (Smedes et al., 2010; Novák et al., 2018), partly in combination with sampling of invertebrates, e.g. mussels (Booij et al., 2006; Pintado-Herrera et al., 2020). However, equilibrium of HOCs between water and passive samplers is approached only very slowly and is hence challenging to achieve within practical time frames. Vrana et al. (2019) found that, despite various efforts to facilitate equilibration for *in-situ* passive sampling, compounds with $\log K_{\text{OW}} > 6$ did not reach equilibrium partitioning between silicone passive samplers and water within 164 days.

Sediment has a high sorption capacity for HOCs and is better suited for passive samplers to estimate bioaccumulation than water (Schmidt and Burgess, 2020). Sediment passive equilibrium sampling can be applied *ex-situ* in the laboratory with equilibrium partitioning achieved within several weeks. Passive sampling of soil or sediments with defined silicone coatings in glass jars (Reichenberg et al., 2008; Maenpaa et al., 2011; Jahnke et al., 2012) as the basis for calculating $C_{\text{Lip}=\text{Sed}}$ (Jahnke et al., 2014) proved to be a suitable approach to determine the thermodynamic potential for bioaccumulation. $C_{\text{Lip}=\text{Sed}}$ was found to be a conservative measure for the measured concentrations in fish muscle tissue, normalized to extracted lipids (C_{Lip}), because fish species of different trophic levels from a Swedish lake usually remained below $C_{\text{Lip}=\text{Sed}}$ (Jahnke et al., 2014) and approximated $C_{\text{Lip}=\text{Sed}}$ at high trophic levels above 4 (Smedes et al., 2020). Schäfer et al. (2015) showed that this approach also worked reliably for bream from different sites in River Elbe, Germany.

As an alternative to sediment and water, suspended particulate matter (SPM) can be used to provide fugacity-based estimates for biota exposure to contaminants (Schubert et al., 2012). SPM shares the high sorptive capacity for HOCs of sediments, yet is constantly mixed and in dynamic exchange with the water column and pelagic biota, and can hence be a more direct proxy for the thermodynamic potential for bioaccumulation in fish than sediments (Witt et al., 2001). Like sediments,

SPM can reach equilibrium partitioning in an *ex-situ* experiment with a thin-layer passive sampling polymer within a period of several weeks even for HOCs with a $\log K_{\text{OW}} > 6$, provided that enough SPM can be collected to ensure negligible depletion (Mayer et al., 2003).

This study aimed to assess whether $C_{\text{Lip}=\text{SPM}}$ is a suitable proxy for C_{Lip} in bream (*Abramis brama*) and zebra mussels (*Dreissena polymorpha*) sampled within the national monitoring program of the German Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB; <https://www.umweltprobenbank.de/en/>). We used representative mixed samples collected in 2018 from the Rivers Elbe, Danube, Saar and Saale. We determined C_{Lip} in fish and mussels for a range of HOCs including eight polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), 14 polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and hexachlorobenzene (HCB) using total extraction and $C_{\text{Lip}=\text{SPM}}$ from polymer-based passive equilibrium sampling of SPM. These results formed the basis to calculate the partitioning status $C_{\text{Lip}}/C_{\text{Lip}=\text{SPM}}$ between biota and SPM. Since $C_{\text{Lip}=\text{SPM}}$ in most cases exceeded C_{Lip} , we suggest $C_{\text{Lip}=\text{SPM}}$ derived from SPM as a suitable proxy for lipid-normalized concentrations (C_{Lip}) in fish and mussels at the different monitoring stations.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Calculation of equilibrium partitioning concentrations in lipids

This study applied the approach of Jahnke et al. (2014) using the concentration found in the silicone DC1–2577 (Dow Chemical Company, USA) as a well-defined reference phase at equilibrium with SPM $C_{\text{Lip}=\text{SPM}}$ in combination with compound-specific $K_{\text{Lip}/\text{Sil}}$ to calculate the equilibrium partitioning concentrations in lipids at equilibrium with an environmental compartment, in this case SPM $C_{\text{Lip}=\text{SPM}}$ according to Eq. (1):

$$C_{\text{Lip}=\text{SPM}} = C_{\text{Sil}=\text{SPM}} \times K_{\text{Lip}/\text{Sil}} \quad (1)$$

For all PCBs and HCB, $K_{\text{Lip}/\text{Sil}}$ data for the silicone polymer DC1–2577 were taken from Gilbert et al. (2016). For the other compounds, no direct partition coefficients for DC1–2577 were available. As an alternative, the silicone polymer Altesil was chosen because of its similar partitioning behavior to DC1–2577 (Gilbert et al., 2016). Hence, $K_{\text{Lip}/\text{Sil}}$ for PAHs $K_{\text{Lip}/\text{Sil PAH}}$ were calculated using lipid/silicone partition coefficients of the silicone Altesil $K_{\text{Lip}/\text{Altesil}}$ provided by Smedes et al. (2017) and lipid/silicone partition coefficients $K_{\text{Lip}/\text{Sil PAH}}$ for PAHs provided by Gilbert et al. (2016) (Eq. 2). See also Tables S8 and S9 in the SI for further details.

$$K_{\text{Lip}/\text{Sil PAH}} = \text{mean} \left(\frac{K_{\text{Lip}/\text{Sil}}}{K_{\text{Lip}/\text{Altesil}}} \right) \times K_{\text{Lip}/\text{Altesil PAH}} \quad (2)$$

2.2. Chemicals

Analytical standards used for quantification consisted of eight PCBs, 14 PAHs and HCB. In addition to those model compounds, we also measured other pollutants (Table S1) which are not discussed here due to the lack of published lipid/silicone partition coefficients ($K_{\text{Lip}/\text{Sil}}$) that would have been needed for conversion of the concentrations in the silicone (C_{Sil}) to $C_{\text{Lip}=\text{SPM}}$. Relevant stable isotope-labeled internal standards (IS) used in this study consisted of seven $^{13}\text{C}_6$ -labeled PCBs, six multi-deuterated PAHs and $^{13}\text{C}_3$ -HCB in an ethyl acetate stock solution (1000 pg/ μL , Table S1).

PAHs can be grouped into low molecular weight PAHs ($\log K_{\text{OW}}$, here: Fluorene (4.14), Acenaphthylene (3.80), Phenanthrene (4.62)) composed of up to three aromatic rings and high molecular weight PAHs ($\log K_{\text{OW}}$, here: Pyrene (5.06), Chrysene (5.67), Benzo(a)anthracene (5.83), Benzo(b)fluoranthene (5.83), Benzo(k)fluoranthene (5.85), Benzo(a)pyrene (5.99), Dibenz(a,h)anthracene (6.51) and Benzo(ghi)perylene (6.60)), which contain four or more rings. We discuss these PAH groups separately due to their differences in bioaccumulation

potential.

2.3. Sample types and sampling sites

All samples were provided by the German Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB; <https://www.umweltprobenbank.de/en/>), collected and processed according to their standard procedures (Klein et al., 2018; Ricking et al., 2017; Teubner et al., 2018; Ruedel et al., 2008; Ruedel and Weingärtner, 2008). In short, the entire soft body of zebra mussels of at least 100 individuals per site was sampled between September and November 2018 and pooled (Teubner et al., 2018). Mussels were raised on special racks in a reference water body (Lake Constance, Germany) and then deployed in the target river for one year. Muscle tissue of bream was collected of 20 individuals per location in the late summer of 2018 after spawning (Klein et al., 2018). The intended age of the sampled individuals was between 8 and 12 years. The actual age of our sample set, as subsequently determined using their scales and opercula (Klein et al., 2018), differed depending on site-specific environmental factors and was (mean \pm standard deviation): River Saale 11.3 ± 5.8 ; River Danube 9.7 ± 3.6 ; River Saar 4.8 ± 1.4 ; River Elbe 7.9 ± 2.4 . Tissues were frozen immediately after sampling, pooled for each sampling site and homogenized using a cryomill (Ruedel et al., 2008; UBA, 2008; Klein et al., 2018). Stable isotope ratios of nitrogen and carbon were determined as described in Corman et al. (2018) from homogenized mixed samples of bream and mussel for each sampling site, respectively. The trophic level (TL) for bream (Table 1) was calculated based on the nitrogen isotope ratio increment of 2.3 between each trophic level, taking zebra mussels as a base at TL= 2 (see also Table S5), assuming they are the primary consumer of the trophic network (McCutchan et al., 2003; Kosfeld et al., 2021). SPM was sampled continuously monthly over the entire year 2018 using passive sedimentation boxes (Ricking et al., 2017; Schulze, 2007), which were deployed in a monitoring station with continuous river water flow-through to allow collection of freshly equilibrated SPM over time, or placed into the stream 1 m below the surface. Boxes were emptied every month and the SPM was sieved (<2 mm), frozen, freeze-dried and pooled to annual samples, to form an integrative mixed sample for the entire year according to the ESB guideline described by Ricking et al., 2017. This procedure regularly generates a substantial mass of SPM (100–200 g dry mass per month), where the cumulated sample reflects the average situation over the month. All ESB samples were divided into identical subsamples and archived under cryogenic conditions (stored below -130 °C) (Ruedel and Weingärtner, 2008).

Sampling sites for this study were chosen to have the most diverse contamination patterns and levels as possible: River Elbe near Cumlosen represents a large catchment area across Germany, River Danube near Jochenstein was our background reference site (for burdens of legacy HOCs) which is characterized by the alpine mountain range in its catchment area, River Saale near Wettin represents a catchment characterized by chemical industry, and the catchment area of River Saar near Rehlingen was chosen as heavily industrialized and densely populated area.

2.4. Exhaustive extraction of biota tissues

The homogenized tissues of mussels and bream were extracted using

the modified method described by Jensen et al. (2003). Briefly, tissue samples were extracted in three steps with mixtures of 2-propanol, diethyl ether and hexane in different compositions. The collected extracts were then transferred to acetonitrile and underwent a cleanup using 6 mL Captiva EMR-Lipid cartridges (Agilent Technologies, USA) as described by Muz et al. (2021), followed by a second cleanup step using 30 mg of PSA sorbent (Agilent Technologies, USA). For a detailed description see Text S2 in the SI.

The quantification of the lipid contents of the biota tissues was done by non-chlorinated solvent extraction following Smedes (1999) with minor modifications. See Text S3 in the SI for details.

2.5. Passive sampling of suspended particulate matter

Passive sampling of SPM followed a modified approach described by (Reichenberg et al., 2008; Maenpaa et al., 2011; Jahnke et al., 2012). Briefly, 10 g of freeze-dried SPM samples and 40 mL of bi-distilled water were used to create a standardized suspension of adequate consistency to allow for adequate mixing and contact with the silicone; these suspensions were rolled in silicone-coated jars (silicone used: Dowsil DC 1–2577, Dow Chemical Company, USA) with coating thicknesses (mean silicone mass) of 0.5 (5.5 mg), 1 (8.5 mg), 2 (16.5 mg), 4 (47.3 mg), 8 (69.4 mg) and 16 μ m (107.0 mg) for three weeks. Reichenberg et al. (2008) showed that two weeks of rolling are sufficient to reach equilibrium even for compounds with a $\log K_{OW} > 7$. The equilibration time was extended to three weeks in this study as an additional safety measure. Following removal of the sample and thorough surface wiping, the chemicals in the silicone coating were extracted with ethyl acetate. See Text S4 in the SI for a detailed description. To check that depletion was negligible and equilibrium was attained during equilibrium passive sampling of the SPM samples, we processed six coating thicknesses (0.5, 1, 2, 4, 8 and 16 μ m). Details are given in SI Text S5 with an example presented in Table S2 and results listed in Table S3. For SPM samples with a TOC content of > 6% all silicone coating thicknesses were used for the determination of equilibrium partitioning concentrations up to a $\log K_{OW}$ of 5.7. For the compounds with $\log K_{OW} > 5.71$, the 16 μ m coating could not be included due to non-negligible depletion. For SPM from River Danube with the lowest TOC fraction, the 16 μ m coatings could only be used for a $\log K_{OW}$ up to 4.1, until a $\log K_{OW}$ of 6.6 coatings until 8 μ m could be used, and only 4 μ m of coating was suitable for compounds with a $\log K_{OW} > 6.6$ without risking depletion of the SPM by the passive sampling material.

2.6. Chemical analysis

Chemical analysis was done on a 7890 A GC System coupled to a 7000 GC/MS TripleQuad (Agilent Technologies, USA). Mass transitions of precursor/product ions were recorded in dynamic multiple reaction monitoring (dMRM) mode that combines excellent specificity with high sensitivity (for details see Text S1 (Table S1) in the SI).

2.7. Quality assurance and quality control

We compared the lipid-normalized concentrations from total solvent extraction of Benzo(a)anthracene, Benzo(ghi)perylene and Pyrene in mussel soft body and PCB 101, PCB 118, PCB 138, PCB 153 and HCB in

Table 1

Biometric and physiological data (mean with standard deviation, SD) of the bream samples determined as part of the ESB monitoring program (except for lipid content, this study) for 2018. The K-factor = $100 \cdot (\text{weight}/\text{length}^3)$ represents a measure for the general physiological condition of individuals (Nash et al., 2006).

River	Lipid content (mean \pm SD %)	Length (mean \pm SD, cm)	Age (mean \pm SD, y)	Trophic level (TL)	Weight (mean \pm SD, g)	K-factor (mean \pm SD)
Saale	3.3 ± 0.0	56.1 ± 6.3	11.3 ± 5.8	3.0	2077 ± 595	1.15 ± 0.15
Danube	3.2 ± 0.2	51.8 ± 4.2	9.8 ± 3.7	3.1	1970 ± 437	1.32 ± 0.08
Saar	4.4 ± 0.8	50.5 ± 4.0	4.8 ± 1.5	2.3	1788 ± 484	1.36 ± 0.12
Elbe	1.3 ± 0.2	50.3 ± 3.4	8.0 ± 2.5	3.4	1260 ± 195	1.01 ± 0.08

breast muscle tissue generated in this study to independent results gained for identical subsamples available in the online data base of the German ESB (<https://www.umweltprobenbank.de/en/documents/investigations/>). This quality-assured data was used for cross-validation of our measurements. Due to the importance of quality assurance and quality control along the entire process of sampling, equilibration, extraction and analysis, our specific quality measures regarding our applied methodology for lipid determination, biota extraction and analyte detection and quantification are described in detail in Text S6 (Table S4).

2.8. Statistical processing

The statistical computing environment R with the packages “FactoMineR” and “factoextra” was used to conduct a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (RCORETEAM, 2020).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of bream tissue samples

The lipid contents of the bream tissues and additional physiological data are given in Table 1. Lipid contents of the mussel samples were $1.5 \pm 0.1\%$, $1.0 \pm 0.01\%$, $0.6 \pm 0.1\%$ and $0.5 \pm 0.1\%$ for samples from the Rivers Elbe, Danube, Saar and Saale in 2018, respectively.

3.2. Direct measurement in zebra mussels and bream

Tables S10 and S11 in the SI spread sheet list amongst others the lipid-normalized concentrations C_{Lip} measured in the pooled samples of zebra mussels and bream, respectively. In general, there was a good agreement between the C_{Lip} data in bream and mussels of this study and the corresponding data sets provided by the ESB (see Fig. S1), with deviations between factors ($C_{Lip}/ESB\ C_{Lip}$) 0.31 (Pyrene in mussels from River Danube) up to 5.54 (Phenanthrene in mussels from River Saale).

3.3. Partitioning status for zebra mussels

Table S11 contains all relevant zebra mussel-associated data. Equilibrium partitioning concentrations in lipids at equilibrium with SPM ($C_{Lip=SPM}$) from passive equilibrium sampling were used to assess the partitioning status between biota and SPM at the different sampling sites by comparing C_{Lip} from total extraction of mussels with the equilibrium partitioning concentration $C_{Lip=SPM}$ (Eq. 3).

$$\text{Partitioning status} = \frac{C_{Lip}}{C_{Lip=SPM}} \quad (3)$$

The partitioning status is a measure for the ratio in concentrations of HOCs between lipid from biota tissue and model lipids at equilibrium with the SPM. The $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ was generally below 1.0 for mussels (Fig. 1).

For PCBs in mussels, PCB 118 in River Elbe showed the lowest $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ value (mean \pm SD) ($0.02 \pm <0.01$) and PCB 52 in River Elbe had the highest value (0.22 ± 0.05) (Fig. 1B). For the PAHs, Benzo(ghi)perylene in River Elbe (Fig. 1B) marked the minimum ($0.008 \pm <0.01$) and Fluorene in River Danube (Fig. 1C) the maximum values (0.66 ± 0.16).

HCB in mussels could only be quantified in samples from River Saale ($0.006 \pm <0.001$) (Fig. 1D) and River Elbe ($0.02 \pm <0.01$) (Fig. 1B).

Zebra Mussels accumulate HOCs via gill respiration from the surrounding water and by digestion of their main food source (phyto-) plankton (Meador et al., 1995). (Phyto-)Plankton has a fast growth rate and hence shows a dilution effect towards the accumulation of HOCs (Kwon et al., 2016). Thus, biomagnification of HOCs for mussels is minor compared to respirational bioconcentration from the environment (Mackay et al., 2013; Smedes et al., 2020). Like other mollusks, they only have limited metabolic elimination capacities for PAHs (Meador et al., 1995) and are therefore frequently used as a bioindicator in aquatic monitoring programs.

As filter feeders, mussels are in close contact with SPM, and in combination with their lower biotransformation capacity for PAHs

Fig. 1. Site-specific plots for the mean partitioning status $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ plotted against $\log K_{ow}$ values of PCBs, HCB and PAHs for the Rivers Saar (A), Elbe (B), Danube (C) and Saale (D). The mean was calculated from the partition status derived from $C_{SIL=SPM}$ measured in non-depletive silicone coating thicknesses (max $n = 6$). Error bars represent the standard deviation of the mean partitioning status. The solid line marks equilibrium, that is, a partitioning status of 1.0, the dashed lines above and below mark a factor of 2 and the dotted lines mark a factor of 10 above and below equilibrium partitioning, respectively.

opposed to bream, SPM was postulated to act as a direct, yet conservative, proxy for their internal concentration controlled by bio-concentration (Meador et al., 1995). The linear relationship between the partitioning status $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ and $\log K_{OW}$ (Fig. 2) demonstrates that this assumption only holds true for more hydrophilic chemicals, where a partitioning status of 1.0 between mussels and SPM can be approximated for compounds with a $\log K_{OW}$ between 2 and 3. The partitioning status decreased in mussels with increasing hydrophobicity of the compound.

3.4. Partitioning status for bream

Bream-related data are listed in the SI spread sheet (Table S10). The levels of $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ for PCBs in bream were the lowest for PCB 180 in River Saar (0.13 ± 0.02) and the highest for PCB 101 in River Danube (1.53 ± 0.41) (Fig. 1).

HCB reached the highest $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ level in River Danube (0.41 ± 0.23) and had the minimum in River Elbe (0.14 ± 0.03). Consistent with this observation, HCB previously showed a situation close to equilibrium partitioning with sediment for mussels and different fish species in a Swedish lake (Jahnke et al., 2014).

For PAHs, Chrysene had the lowest $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ level in River Saar (0.0002 ± 0.0001) and Fluorene marked the highest $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ level in River Danube (0.59 ± 0.15). Along with Fluorene, other low molecular weight PAHs in bream (Acenaphthylene: $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ 0.077–0.64, Phenanthrene: 0.047–0.31) remained at a relatively high $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ compared to the more hydrophobic high molecular weight PAHs, with Chrysene marking the compound with the lowest $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ in River Saar (0.0002) and Benzo(b)fluoranthene the highest $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ but still relatively low partitioning status (0.05, River Elbe). In general, PAHs can be metabolized and eliminated by fish (Meador et al., 1995). Passive sampling cannot simulate metabolic transformation of HOCs in biota, but it still provides valuable information on the potential uptake from the environment. Low molecular weight PAHs in bream and mussels across all sampling sites were at similar $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ (mean \pm SD): Acenaphthylene with a $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ in bream of 0.24 ± 0.14 and in mussels of 0.31 ± 0.13 , Fluorene 0.33 ± 0.17 and 0.32 ± 0.19 , and Phenanthrene 0.14 ± 0.10 and 0.21 ± 0.10 , respectively. This observation indicates a common uptake and elimination pathway via the gills.

Data of trophic levels of bream and the average age of the sampled individuals for each sampling site was provided by the ESB (Table 1). The age and trophic level of fish can be important parameters for certain compounds to explain bioaccumulation in food webs, although age is

Fig. 2. Partitioning status ($C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$) plotted against $\log K_{OW}$ values of PCBs and PAHs in mussels from all four sampling sites. The solid line marks equilibrium, that is, a partitioning status of 1.0, the dashed lines above and below mark a factor of 2 above and below equilibrium partitioning, respectively, and the dotted line marks a factor of 10 below equilibrium partitioning. The thick black line represents the linear regression of $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ with $\log K_{OW}$. The shaded area shows the confidence interval of the linear model.

more important for the prediction of PCB accumulation (McIntyre and Beauchamp, 2007). By comparing $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ of selected compounds covering all compound classes (PAHs, PCBs and HCB) and a broad range of physicochemical properties between the different fish sample pools, an approximation of the partitioning status towards 1.0 with increasing age becomes apparent in Fig. 3A. The increase was not observed in fish from River Saale though, where despite the highest average age, the partitioning status of all displayed compounds was lower than in the River Danube. A reason for this observation might be the high variance in the partitioning status of PCB 52 due to a high silicone-normalized concentration (31.59 pg/mg) from the 1 μ m coated jar replicate. In addition, PCB 153 could only be quantified in one replicate of SPM from River Danube. The partitioning status of PCB 180 as very lipophilic, strongly biomagnifying chemical shows a steady increase with increasing age. With the exception of the highly variable and therefore uncertain PCB 52 concentration in River Danube, $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ remained < 1.0 , which means that the SPM can be used as a conservative proxy for C_{Lip} in bream and a realistic proxy for older fish (Fig. 3A).

In order to further explore the influence of age, trophic level and other parameters on the partitioning status of bream between the sampling sites, a principal component analysis (PCA) was conducted (Abdi and Williams, 2010), using averaged physiological data for each sampling site: age, trophic level, K-factor (Table 1) and lipid content, partitioning status $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$, $C_{Lip=SPM}$ and C_{Lip} of PCBs and HCB, and the respective $\log K_{OW}$ for those compounds. The PAHs were excluded from this analysis since they are known to be metabolized by fish and would hence result in a bias of the variance of the data set. The PCA results are given in Fig. 3B and indicate a strong positive correlation between age and $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ and a less significant positive correlation to the trophic level. A negative correlation was observed between $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ and $\log K_{OW}$ and $C_{Lip=SPM}$ (more details in SI Tables S6 and S7).

3.5. Passive equilibrium sampling of SPM as a monitoring tool and proxy for bioaccumulation

Schäfer et al. (2015) sampled sediment from three sites along River Elbe in 2012 with a similar equilibrium passive sampling approach as the one used in this study. They compared the equilibrium partitioning concentrations of PCBs 28, 52, 101, 118, 138, 153 and 180 to lipid-normalized concentrations in bream C_{Lip} plotted vs. lipids at equilibrium with sediment $C_{Lip=Sediment}$. A linear regression forced through the origin yielded a slope of 0.327 for the sampling site Cumlosen at the River Elbe. In the present study, the same regression was made for C_{Lip} vs. $C_{Lip=SPM}$ for the same PCBs at the identical sampling site sampled in 2018, yielding a slope of 0.666 (see also SI Fig. S2), thus putting SPM and sediment into the same range of partitioning status for a fish species from the same riverine ecosystem. A study conducted in a lake ecosystem by Jahnke et al. (2014) described the partitioning situation between biota and sediment in Lake Ången, Sweden. The partitioning status $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=Sediment}$ of the same set of PCBs as above in Lake Ången stayed between 0.01 and 0.1 for duck mussels (*Anodonta anatina*) and between 0.1 and 0.5 for common roach (*Rutilus rutilus*, trophic level: 3.0 Froese and Pauly, 2019). In the present study, $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ for the same PCBs in zebra mussel were in a similar range, between 0.004 (PCB 180 in River Danube) and 0.277 (PCB 52 in River Elbe).

The present study revealed a wide range of $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ (Fig. 1) characterized by site-specific factors (Fig. 3B). As shown in Fig. 3A, with increasing age the concentrations in bream were in many cases closer to equilibrium partitioning. In individual cases (six out of 57 observations) C_{Lip} slightly exceeded $C_{Lip=SPM}$. In those cases, SPM was not a conservative proxy for bream exposure, e.g. in bream sampled from River Danube with PCB 101 reaching the highest partitioning status in this study (1.53). Trophic position was positively correlated

Fig. 3. (A) Plot of the partitioning status ($C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$) of selected compounds quantified in the fish sample pools from different sites vs. the average age of the sampled bream. Their age is listed in Table. The mean was calculated from the partitioning status derived from $C_{Sil=SPM}$ measured in the non-depletive silicone coating thicknesses (max $n = 6$). Error bars represent the standard deviation of the mean partitioning status. (B) Correlation plot generated from PCA results. Positively correlating variables are grouped together, negatively correlating variables are in an opposite position. The closer a variable to a principal component, the stronger their correlation. The further away a variable from the origin, the better it is represented by the factor map generated by the two dimensions.

with $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$, but age remained the most influential parameter on the partitioning status for bream (Fig. 3B). Mussel-derived $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ did not show any exceedance of 1.0 but remained at 0.66 (Fluorene in River Danube) or below, likely due to their low trophic position and very limited biomagnification, making SPM a conservative proxy for their internal concentration (Fig. 2). For mussels, a linear relationship between $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM}$ and $\log K_{OW}$ was observed with $C_{Lip}/C_{Lip=SPM} = -0.518 \times \log K_{OW} + 0.281$ ($r^2 = 0.53$) based on all quantified compounds in this species across all rivers (Fig. 2), which underlines the suitability of SPM as a robust proxy for bioconcentration in zebra mussels. For bream, SPM is a conservative proxy for the internal concentration of the analyzed HOCs with a $\log K_{OW} < 5$. For strongly biomagnifying compounds ($\log K_{OW} > 5$) SPM can lose its conservative character if certain conditions, like high age and/or high trophic position are met.

Regarding passive sampling of water as a proxy for the internal exposure of fish, Smedes et al. (2020) reported that C_{Lip} for PCBs in fish with trophic level < 4 did not exceed $C_{Lip=Water}$. In the present study, the partitioning status was > 1.0 for the PCBs 52, 101, 118, 138 and 153 in bream in River Danube and PCB 118 in River Saale. Mixed samples of bream muscle in this study had a trophic level of 2.3–3.4, with TL = 3.0 at River Saale and TL = 3.1 at River Danube.

SPM has the advantage as a compartment for passive sampling opposed to water that highly lipophilic compounds ($\log K_{OW} > 6$) are easier to detect and an actual equilibrium partitioning can be established in a controlled laboratory environment within a reasonable time frame (here: 3 weeks). Compared to sediment, SPM offers a more mobile and dynamic compartment for passive sampling that is constantly mixed and in close contact with the water phase. Passive sampling of SPM is easy to standardize, straightforward and fugacity-based, without major clean-up steps required. This approach prevents the loss of non-persistent compounds and makes SPM a promising matrix for monitoring in the aquatic environment that is free of ethical concerns. Those features render SPM an interesting source of basic information for aquatic food web models (Ghosh et al., 2021), and it is useful as a surrogate for biological monitoring data. A direct application of SPM as a proxy could be useful for fish for human consumption, as individuals of higher age and trophic position are usually consumed.

Funding sources

T.W. received funding from the UFZ PhD College “Proxies of the Eco-Exposome”. This study was partially supported by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (grant agreement no. 715173, CHEMO-RISK). Some of the analytical instruments used in this study are part of the major infrastructure initiative CITEPro (Chemicals in the Environment Profiler) funded by the Helmholtz Association.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. T. W. and A.J. conceived and designed the experiments. T.W. performed all laboratory work, quantified the data and designed the figures. S.A. contributed to the development of the instrumental / analytical methods. T.W. and A.J. wrote the manuscript with input from all co-authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Jörg Watzke for help with sample preparation and Eva Reiter for help with the preparation of the coated jars. We acknowledge Aleksandra Piotrowska, Sandra Jäsch and Martin Krauss for their expertise and support with all GC/MS-related issues. We also thank each member of the “Chemometers Group” for the good discussions and valuable comments regarding this study. The German Environmental Specimen Bank is funded by the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety. The committed work of all ESB team members at the German Environment Agency, Trier University, Federal Institute of Hydrology, Eurofins GfA Lab

Service GmbH and Fraunhofer IME is gratefully acknowledged.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2022.113285.

References

- Abdi, H., Williams, L.J., 2010. Principal component analysis. *WIREs Comput. Stat.* 2, 433–459.
- Booij, K., et al., 2006. Environmental monitoring of hydrophobic organic contaminants: the case of mussels versus semipermeable membrane devices. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 40, 3893–3900.
- Corman, A.M., et al., 2018. Decreasing $\delta(13)C$ and $\delta(15)N$ values in four coastal species at different trophic levels indicate a fundamental food-web shift in the southern North and Baltic Seas between 1988 and 2016. *Environ. Monit. Assess.* 190, 461.
- Fliedner, A., et al., 2016. Biota monitoring and the Water Framework Directive-can normalization overcome shortcomings in sampling strategies? *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res. Int.* 23, 21927–21939.
- Froese, R., Pauly, D., 2019. FishBase. World Wide Web Electronic Publication. World Wide Web electronic publication.
- Ghosh, U., et al., 2021. Deconvoluting thermodynamics from biology in the aquatic food web model. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 40, 2145–2155.
- Gilbert, D., et al., 2016. Polymers as reference partitioning phase: polymer calibration for an analytically operational approach to quantify multimedia phase partitioning. *Anal. Chem.* 88, 5818–5826.
- Gobas, F., et al., 2018. A chemical activity approach to exposure and risk assessment of chemicals: focus articles are part of a regular series intended to sharpen understanding of current and emerging topics of interest to the scientific community. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 37, 1235–1251.
- Gobas, F.A.P.C., et al., 1999. Mechanism of biomagnification in fish under laboratory and field conditions. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 33, 133–141.
- Jahnke, A., et al., 2008. Equilibrium sampling: partitioning of organochlorine compounds from lipids into polydimethylsiloxane. *Chemosphere* 73, 1575–1581.
- Jahnke, A., et al., 2012. Sensitive equilibrium sampling to study polychlorinated biphenyl disposition in Baltic Sea sediment. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 46, 10114–10122.
- Jahnke, A., et al., 2014. Equilibrium sampling to determine the thermodynamic potential for bioaccumulation of persistent organic pollutants from sediment. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 48, 11352–11359.
- Jensen, S., et al., 2003. A quantitative lipid extraction method for residue analysis of fish involving nonhalogenated solvents. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 51, 5607–5611.
- Kidd, K.A., et al., 1998. Effects of trophic position and lipid on organochlorine concentrations in fishes from subarctic lakes in Yukon Territory. *Can. J. Fish. Aquat. Sci.* 55, 869–881.
- Klein, R., Paulus, M., Tarricone, K., Teubner, D., 2018. Guideline for Sampling and Sample Processing Bream (*Abramis brama*) Version 2.0.4. Umweltprobenbank. German Environment Agency, Dessau-Rosslau, Germany.
- Kosfeld, V., et al., 2021. Food web on ice: a pragmatic approach to investigate the trophic magnification of chemicals of concern. *Environmental Sciences. Europe* 33, 93.
- Kwon, J.H., et al., 2016. Including bioconcentration kinetics for the prioritization and interpretation of regulatory aquatic toxicity tests of highly hydrophobic chemicals. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 50, 12004–12011.
- Macdonald, R., et al., 2002. Contaminant amplification in the environment. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 36, 456A–462A.
- Mackay, D., et al., 2013. Mathematical relationships between metrics of chemical bioaccumulation in fish. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 32, 1459–1466.
- Maenpaa, K., et al., 2011. Equilibrium sampling of persistent and bioaccumulative compounds in soil and sediment: comparison of two approaches to determine equilibrium partitioning concentrations in lipids. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 45, 1041–1047.
- Mayer, P., et al., 2003. Equilibrium sampling devices. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 37, 184A–191A.
- McCutchan Jr., J.H., et al., 2003. Variation in trophic shift for stable isotope ratios of carbon, nitrogen, and sulfur. *Oikos* 102, 378–390.
- McIntyre, J.K., Beauchamp, D.A., 2007. Age and trophic position dominate bioaccumulation of mercury and organochlorines in the food web of Lake Washington. *Sci. Total Environ.* 372, 571–584.
- McLeod, A., et al., 2014. Effect of season and habitat on PCB bioaccumulation by caged bluegill sunfish deployed in a Great Lakes area of concern. *Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* 93, 1–6.
- Meador, J.P., et al., 1995. Bioaccumulation of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons by marine organisms. In: Ware, G.W. (Ed.), *Reviews of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*. Springer, New York, New York, NY, pp. 79–165.
- Muz, M., et al., 2021. Removing disturbing matrix constituents from biota extracts from total extraction and silicone-based passive sampling. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 40, 2693–2704.
- Nash, R., et al., 2006. The origin of Fulton's condition factor - setting the record straight. *Fisheries* 31, 236–238.
- Novák, J., et al., 2018. Effect-based monitoring of the Danube River using mobile passive sampling. *Sci. Total Environ.* 636, 1608–1619.
- Pintado-Herrera, M.G., et al., 2020. Passive samplers vs sentinel organisms: one-year monitoring of priority and emerging contaminants in coastal waters. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 54, 6693–6702.
- Qiao, P., et al., 2000. Relative contributions of aqueous and dietary uptake of hydrophobic chemicals to the body burden in juvenile rainbow trout. *Arch. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* 39, 369–377.
- RCoreTeam, R.: *A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria, 2020.
- Reichenberg, F., et al., 2008. Determining the chemical activity of hydrophobic organic compounds in soil using polymer coated vials. *Chem. Central J.* 2, 8.
- Ruedel, H., Uhlig, S., Weingärtner, M., Pulverisation and Homogenisation of Environmental Samples by Cryomilling V 2.0.0. Umweltprobenbank des Bundes, Fraunhofer Institute for Molecular Biology and Applied Ecology, Auf dem Aberg 1, D-57392 Schmallenberg and German Environment Agency, Dessau-Rosslau, Germany, 2008.
- Ruedel, H., Weingärtner, M., Storage of Environmental Samples under Cryogenic Conditions V 2.0.0. Umweltprobenbank des Bundes, Fraunhofer Institute for Molecular Biology and Applied Ecology, Auf dem Aberg 1, D-57392 Schmallenberg and German Environment Agency, Dessau-Rosslau, Germany, 2008.
- Ricking, M., Keller, M., Heininger, P., Körner, A., et al., 2017. Richtlinie zur Probenahme und Probenbearbeitung Schwebstoffe V 4.0.3. Umweltprobenbank des Bundes. Freie Universität Berlin, Fachbereich Geowissenschaften, Arbeitsbereich Hydrogeologie.
- Schäfer, S., et al., 2015. Equilibrium sampling of polychlorinated biphenyls in River Elbe sediments – linking bioaccumulation in fish to sediment contamination. *Chemosphere* 138, 856–862.
- Schmidt, S.N., Burgess, R.M., 2020. Evaluating polymeric sampling as a tool for predicting the bioaccumulation of polychlorinated biphenyls by fish and shellfish. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 54, 9729–9741.
- Schubert, B., et al., 2012. Monitoring of contaminants in suspended particulate matter as an alternative to sediments. *Trends Anal. Chem.* 36, 58–70.
- Schulze, T., et al., 2007. The German environmental specimen bank. *J. Soils Sediment.* 7, 361–367.
- Smedes, F., 1999. Determination of total lipid using non-chlorinated solvents. *Analyst* 124, 1711–1718.
- Smedes, F., et al., 2010. The use of passive sampling in WFD monitoring: the possibilities of silicon rubber as a passive sampler. *Delta, Delft*.
- Smedes, F., et al., 2017. Partitioning of hydrophobic organic contaminants between polymer and lipids for two silicones and low density polyethylene. *Chemosphere* 186, 948–957.
- Smedes, F., et al., 2020. Unraveling the relationship between the concentrations of hydrophobic organic contaminants in freshwater fish of different trophic levels and water using passive sampling. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 54, 7942–7951.
- Teubner, D., Klein, R., Tarricone, K., Paulus, M., 2018. Guideline for Sampling and Sample Processing Zebra Mussel (*Dreissena polymorpha*) V 2.1.1. Umweltprobenbank. German Environment Agency, Dessau-Rosslau, Germany.
- Vrana, B., et al., 2019. Chasing equilibrium passive sampling of hydrophobic organic compounds in water. *Sci. Total Environ.* 664, 424–435.
- Witt, G., et al., 2001. Using fluffy layer material to study the fate of particle-bound organic pollutants in the southern Baltic Sea. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 35, 1567–1573.